

TEACHER PREPARATION METHODS FOR EFFECTIVELY ORGANIZING LESSONS

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Annotation: In this article, the art of music enriches the spiritual world of a person, its influence on the conscious and spiritual world of a person, a practical tool of moral and aesthetic education, the role of music in the life of society and its influence on the field of music in our country. attention is fully informed.

Keywords: personality, art, spirituality, music, education, management, lesson, student, theory, teacher, society.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada musiqa san'ati shaxsning ma'naviy dunyosini boyitish, insonning ongli va ma'naviy dunyosiga ta'siri, axloqiy va estetik tarbiyaning amaliy vositasi ekanligi, musiqaning jamiyat hayotida tutgan o'rni va yurtimizdagi musiqa sohasiga bo'lgan e'tibor haqida to'liq ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: shaxs, san'at, ma'naviyat, musiqa, tarbiya, boshqaruv, dars, o'quvchi nazariya, o'qituvchi, jamiyat.

Аннотация: В данной статье музыкальное искусство обогащает духовный мир человека, его влияние на сознательный и духовный мир человека, практические средства нравственного и эстетического воспитания, роль музыки в жизни общества и его Влияние на сферу музыки в нашей стране. Внимание полностью информировано.

Ключевые слова: личность, искусство, духовность, музыка, образование, менеджмент, урок, ученик, теория, учитель, общество.

One of the important conditions for establishing and maintaining order in the classroom is the teacher's thorough preparation for lessons. In order for the lesson to be successful and my child to get a good education, it is necessary for the teacher to know the material given in the lesson very well and master it thoroughly. It is necessary to memorize the text, melody and choir voices of the works studied in all classes. [1] When teaching singing and performing this poet with children, the teacher should be very well versed in accompanying on a musical instrument without difficulty, without mistakes, almost without looking at the notes.

They can play a melody or choral score with one hand and control the children's singing with the other hand should be able to conduct. The

conversation about the works being performed should be well-thought-out and interesting. Instilling a love of music in students depends on how the teacher organizes music listening in the school. [2] When preparing for the lesson, he should have a good idea of the amount of music literacy he wants to give to the children in this lesson, and he should think about the method of conveying this knowledge to the children. Other activities of the teacher in the music literacy part of the lesson to consider how to better connect with, demonstratively must determine the choice of tools, examples, tests, exercises, and homework.

The teacher should carefully think about the topic of the conversation about the song, choose the most important information to tell the children, what new knowledge can be given to the children based on the verbal and musical material of the song. it is necessary to think. [3] Also, according to the song teaching methodology, the teacher determines the areas that require special attention while learning the song, selects exercises that will help to learn the song faster and overcome the difficult parts found in the piece. The use of literary works, stories, fragments of short stories, poems and reproductions of famous artists in order to make the lesson interesting will give good results.

All this enhances the emotional impact of music and helps expand children's knowledge. We know that the dismissal bell creates a conditioned reflex in children, and it involves paying attention to the teacher's words.[4] They don't give. So call the homework until, in a calm situation, how to do it perfectly should be given in an explained state. If the puzzle is given from a book, its pages should be written on the board and checked if the children write it down in their diaries.

Music to the topics and works given to the students in the lesson personal attitude of the teacher is also important. From the outside the work of a teacher compared to a person without experience it seems kind of boring. It is the same again from year to year the topic, those rules, works, exercises are being studied looks like In fact, it is not so. Loves his profession, is positive about it. An engaging teacher adds something new to his lesson every time and does not experience any uniformity in his work. [5] That's how good communication between the teacher and the student is established. This has an effective effect on the educational process. It is not right for the teacher to be too hasty or too slow in leading the pace of the lesson. He should conduct the lesson in a lively, emotional, attractive manner without pause. If the lesson is conducted slowly, with long pauses, if the teacher sits thinking about what else to do, my child's attention is divided, and the lesson becomes ineffective. If the lesson is

conducted at a fast pace, my child's attention will get tired, the brain will get tired and there will be no result in the lesson.

In some cases, it also depends on the personality of the teacher: if he is lazy in life, his words fall out of his mouth, or even if he is in a hurry, the lesson is unsystematic, superficial, somewhat boring and "cold". Therefore, the teacher should always eliminate his shortcomings and work continuously on mastering the methods of conducting the lesson correctly.

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